

1 **Western Diet (WD) predisposes to chronic disease by at least two mechanisms.**

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7 We demonstrate here that Western Diet (WD) predisposes to chronic disease by at least two mechanisms:
8 through chronic senescence impairment involving environmentally (diet)-induced defects in interferon
9 signaling globally, and through propagation of inflammatory signaling via excess lipid consumption. We
10 contrast this to what is described in medicine and scientific literature as a high-fat diet (HFD). We
11 examined total transcription in the tissues in humans following experimentally administered caloric
12 restriction or Western Diet. Muscle biopsies of humans fed a Western Diet displayed marked activation of
13 the obesogenic neuropeptide leptin, which was among the most significant gene expression changes
14 transcriptome-wide, together with reduction of or silencing in a myogenic-adipogenic program featuring
15 silencing of myogenic factor *Myof6*, the muscle related coil coil protein *MURC*, and the brown fat switch
16 *UCP3*. Finally, we examine the transcriptome of healthy and obese individuals to identify and describe
17 genes important for human metabolism induced or controlled by obesity.

18 Citations

19 1. Christ, A., Lauterbach, M. and Latz, E., 2019. Western diet and the immune system: an
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